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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL KHADER SHAMALNAZ** bearing USN **3SU21SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHINAV K** bearing USN **3SU21SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AFEEF AHMED** bearing USN **3SU21SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHMAD SHAFEEK** bearing USN **3SU21SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AISHWARYA GANESH HEGDE** bearing USN **3SU21SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH B** bearing USN **3SU21SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH S** bearing USN **3SU21SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHNAS V A** bearing USN **3SU21SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALAN K WILSON** bearing USN **3SU21SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALBIN THOMAS** bearing USN **3SU21SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEN ALEYAS** bearing USN **3SU21SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEN JOSE** bearing USN **3SU21SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALI HASSAN JUNAID J** bearing USN **3SU21SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMAN S SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU21SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMEENA SABEEBA** bearing USN **3SU21SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUSHREE S** bearing USN **3SU21SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANVITH SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU21SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AREEF M K** bearing USN **3SU21SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARJUN SASEENDRAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHISH SINGH PANWAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHWIN RAMESH** bearing USN **3SU21SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHWINI VENUGOPAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AZAD KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **B MDARSHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHAVISH B** bearing USN **3SU21SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHOOMIKA** bearing USN **3SU21SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CP MOHAMMED AMEEN** bearing USN **3SU21SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHIRAJ KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHIRAG R J** bearing USN **3SU21SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DANUSH KUMAR M** bearing USN **3SU21SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DARSHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DIMPAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DIVYAJAYA J** bearing USN **3SU21SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ENOSH KENNETH PRABHAKAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **EWAPAKA PHAWA** bearing USN **3SU21SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FARHAN RASHEED KAMAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FATHIMA PARAMBAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FATHIMATH MEHAK** bearing USN **3SU21SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FEBIN SUNNY** bearing USN **3SU21SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MORE GAURESH AJIT** bearing USN **3SU21SA040** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARIKIRANA A P** bearing USN **3SU21SA041** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM BADSHAW** bearing USN **3SU21SA042** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM MOHAMMED SAHAF** bearing USN **3SU21SA043** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JANEES P A** bearing USN **3SU21SA044** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JIBIN KURIAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA045** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JISHNU** bearing USN **3SU21SA046** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JOYEL KIRAN PINTO** bearing USN **3SU21SA047** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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DEAN
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K ASHISH KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA048** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K H MAHAMMAD MASOOD** bearing USN **3SU21SA049** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K VIKAS RAO** bearing USN **3SU21SA050** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K Y JOEL** bearing USN **3SU21SA051** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK** bearing USN **3SU21SA052** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAUSHIK N** bearing USN **3SU21SA053** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAVYA M S** bearing USN **3SU21SA054** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA C** bearing USN **3SU21SA055** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KUSHI R** bearing USN **3SU21SA056** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAVANEESH S P** bearing USN **3SU21SA057** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHESH** bearing USN **3SU21SA058** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANIKANTAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA059** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANJUNATH SHET** bearing USN **3SU21SA060** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MASHOOD B M** bearing USN **3SU21SA061** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED HASAN AZMAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA062** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED VASEEM** bearing USN **3SU21SA063** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FAZIL** bearing USN **3SU21SA064** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD HASHIL** bearing USN **3SU21SA065** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD NIFAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA066** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED RIFAZ** bearing USN **3SU21SA067** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ADHIL C H** bearing USN **3SU21SA068** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AFREED** bearing USN **3SU21SA069** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU21SA070** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANEES** bearing USN **3SU21SA071** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASHIQ** bearing USN **3SU21SA072** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FAHEEM LATHEEF K P** bearing USN **3SU21SA073** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARDEEN** bearing USN **3SU21SA074** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARHAZ KHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA075** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FAZIL** bearing USN **3SU21SA076** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED HASSAN JAWAD** bearing USN **3SU21SA077** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED JAMSHEER C.P** bearing USN **3SU21SA078** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED KALANDER B R** bearing USN **3SU21SA079** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MUSTHAFA** bearing USN **3SU21SA080** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NABHAN K** bearing USN **3SU21SA081** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NIHAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA082** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SAHEL S** bearing USN **3SU21SA083** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAZ** bearing USN **3SU21SA084** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ZAHEER HUSSAIN** bearing USN **3SU21SA085** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOIDEEN SAHAD** bearing USN **3SU21SA086** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUEENUDDEN NAWAZ** bearing USN **3SU21SA087** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHAMMAD AFZAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA088** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED MISHAL U V** bearing USN **3SU21SA089** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED RISHAL N.K** bearing USN **3SU21SA091** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAMAL RAFEEK** bearing USN **3SU21SA092** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAMIL M T** bearing USN **3SU21SA093** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHYADDEEN NASIM** bearing USN **3SU21SA094** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NABEEL K P** bearing USN **3SU21SA095** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAFEESATHUL HAADIYAH** bearing USN **3SU21SA096** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAIK PRATVI MOHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA097** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NARESH ULLAS NAIK** bearing USN **3SU21SA098** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NEYEEMA C M** bearing USN **3SU21SA099** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIHAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA100** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIKHITHA M G** bearing USN **3SU21SA101** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **P RAHUL RAJ** bearing USN **3SU21SA102** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PAVAN RAJ** bearing USN **3SU21SA103** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **POORNESH KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA104** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAJWAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA105** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAJWAL K S** bearing USN **3SU21SA106** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAMEETH** bearing USN **3SU21SA107** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PUJARY ABHINAV ANIL** bearing USN **3SU21SA108** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PUNYA J V** bearing USN **3SU21SA109** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RACHANA JN** bearing USN **3SU21SA111** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAKESH K N** bearing USN **3SU21SA112** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAKSHA** bearing USN **3SU21SA113** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAMPRASAD N A** bearing USN **3SU21SA114** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAMNATH SHANBHAG B** bearing USN **3SU21SA115** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIFAZ AHAMED** bearing USN **3SU21SA116** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROHAN RAVI GOUDA** bearing USN **3SU21SA117** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RONIT PHILIP** bearing USN **3SU21SA118** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANIHA** bearing USN **3SU21SA119** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SATHVIKA US** bearing USN **3SU21SA120** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAVITA VISHNOI** bearing USN **3SU21SA121** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SEBASTIAN JOSEPH** bearing USN **3SU21SA122** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHASHANK B KHARVI** bearing USN **3SU21SA123** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRAVYA K** bearing USN **3SU21SA125** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREEJA** bearing USN **3SU21SA126** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREERAKSHA B V** bearing USN **3SU21SA127** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SIMPANA S U** bearing USN **3SU21SA130** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SOHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA131** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SOORAJ BIST** bearing USN **3SU21SA132** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEJESH K** bearing USN **3SU21SA133** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREELAYA.P.V** bearing USN **3SU21SA134** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SRI RAKSHA** bearing USN **3SU21SA135** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUKANYA PADMANABHA HEGDE** bearing USN **3SU21SA136** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUSHANTH M S** bearing USN **3SU21SA137** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SWEEKAR D S BANGERA** bearing USN **3SU21SA138** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **TANMAYA S AIL** bearing USN **3SU21SA139** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THALHATH P.P** bearing USN **3SU21SA140** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THALATUL ANSHARI** bearing USN **3SU21SA141** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THOUFIQ M H** bearing USN **3SU21SA142** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **TUSHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA143** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHNAV VIJAY P K** bearing USN **3SU21SA144** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VARSHA RAMESH NAIK** bearing USN **3SU21SA145** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VARSHA R A** bearing USN **3SU21SA146** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VINISHA SHAINY FERRAO** bearing USN **3SU21SA147** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIBHASHREE B S** bearing USN **3SU21SA148** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMAD ASHRAF** bearing USN **3SU21SA149** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KHADEEJATH SHAMA AHMED SHAFEEQ** bearing USN **3SU21SA150** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAIBHAV P P** bearing USN **3SU21SA151** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL ANSHAD M A** bearing USN **3SU21AI001** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL NUSRATH NUFAIS** bearing USN **3SU21AI002** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHINAV P P** bearing USN **3SU21AI003** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHINAV C** bearing USN **3SU21AI004** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED ANAS NIHAL** bearing USN **3SU21AI006** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH CHANDRA** bearing USN **3SU21AI007** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHAY S** bearing USN **3SU21AI008** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALAN TITUS** bearing USN **3SU21AI009** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANANDHU KS** bearing USN **3SU21AI010** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWIN KRISHNA T** bearing USN **3SU21AI011** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ATHITHYA M N** bearing USN **3SU21AI012** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AVINASH ASWIN** bearing USN **3SU21AI013** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FEBIN JAISON T** bearing USN **3SU21AI014** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FEDIN BINOY** bearing USN **3SU21AI015** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOKUL V GOPAL** bearing USN **3SU21AI016** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARIKRISHNAN P** bearing USN **3SU21AI017** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JUVAID FARHAN THEKUPURAM** bearing USN **3SU21AI018** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA KRISHNAN** bearing USN **3SU21AI019** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LEKSHMI SHALY** bearing USN **3SU21AI020** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SHAHBAS SULTHAN C B** bearing USN **3SU21AI021** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED YASEEN M S** bearing USN **3SU21AI022** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FAIS** bearing USN **3SU21AI023** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASHMAR** bearing USN **3SU21AI024** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED BATHISH B** bearing USN **3SU21AI025** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED BILAL K** bearing USN **3SU21AI026** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED HASAN SHIFNAN** bearing USN **3SU21AI027** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMAD INSHAF B** bearing USN **3SU21AI028** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED JAMSHEER P** bearing USN **3SU21AI029** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MAHSHEYIN M N**, bearing USN **3SU21AI030** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NIHAL ISMAIL P** bearing USN **3SU21AI031** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUBASHIR C** bearing USN **3SU21AI032** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED BISHARATH B K**, bearing USN **3SU21AI033** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED FAYIS P** bearing USN **3SU21AI034** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED MUSTHAFA** bearing USN **3SU21AI035** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED RAZI A** bearing USN **3SU21AI036** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SAHIL A NAVAS** bearing USN **3SU21AI037** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SALMAN ABOOBACKER** bearing USN **3SU21AI038** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAFI M** bearing USN **3SU21AI039** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAHEEN P H** bearing USN **3SU21AI040** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ZAYAN SADIQUE** bearing USN **3SU21AI041** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ZAYED BIN LATHEEF K P** bearing USN **3SU21AI042** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUZAMMIL K**, bearing USN **3SU21AI043** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAWAF** bearing USN **3SU21AI044** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SACHIN V N** bearing USN **3SU21AI045** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANIKA P** bearing USN **3SU21AI046** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHANO SASI** bearing USN **3SU21AI047** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHEIK THANSEER** bearing USN **3SU21AI048** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SINAN V K** bearing USN **3SU21AI049** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SOHAL PUTHAN PURAYIL**, bearing USN **3SU21AI050** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL SAMAD M** bearing USN **3SU21AI052** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **A GOUTHAM** bearing USN **3SU21CC001** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL KHADER M H** bearing USN **3SU21CC002** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAZIQ** bearing USN **3SU21CC003** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHAY PRAKASH** bearing USN **3SU21CC004** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHIJITH M** bearing USN **3SU21CC006** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHINAV NARAYANAN** bearing USN **3SU21CC007** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHIRAM K M** bearing USN **3SU21CC008** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK S** bearing USN **3SU21CC009** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADHISH M** bearing USN **3SU21CC011** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AISWARYA N K** bearing USN **3SU21CC012** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH S S** bearing USN **3SU21CC014** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKBARSHA NAVAS** bearing USN **3SU21CC016** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHIL C** bearing USN **3SU21CC017** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHILRAJ V P** bearing USN **3SU21CC018** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHIL SONICHAN** bearing USN **3SU21CC019** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHAY MADHU** bearing USN **3SU21CC020** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALFEEN RASSAK** bearing USN **3SU21CC021** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMAL T** bearing USN **3SU21CC022** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMISH V** bearing USN **3SU21CC023** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANJITHA K** bearing USN **3SU21CC024** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUAY** bearing USN **3SU21CC025** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUSREE ADIYODI VEETIL** bearing USN **3SU21CC026** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARJUN E S** bearing USN **3SU21CC027** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARJUN MANOJ** bearing USN **3SU21CC028** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWANTH B B** bearing USN **3SU21CC029** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWIN A T** bearing USN **3SU21CC030** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AYISHA SIDHEEKHA S** bearing USN **3SU21CC031** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BRINO PAUL** bearing USN **3SU21CC032** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DARSHAN T** bearing USN **3SU21CC033** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEPIKA R NAIK** bearing USN **3SU21CC034** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANUSH G** bearing USN **3SU21CC035** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOPIKA SUNIL** bearing USN **3SU21CC036** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOUDHAM SANKAR E K** bearing USN **3SU21CC037** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JAVAD HUSSAIN B** bearing USN **3SU21CC038** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JISHNU NARAYANAN K** bearing USN **3SU21CC039** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK P K** bearing USN **3SU21CC040** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KIRAN P K** bearing USN **3SU21CC041** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KIRAN RAJEEV K V** bearing USN **3SU21CC042** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRISHNAN S NAIR** bearing USN **3SU21CC043** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FAWAZ T B** bearing USN **3SU21CC044** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NASHATH** bearing USN **3SU21CC045** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHAI F B** bearing USN **3SU21CC046** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUFEEED M** bearing USN **3SU21CC047** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED RIYAS B** bearing USN **3SU21CC053** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SUHAIL P C** bearing USN **3SU21CC054** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDAKISHOR S** bearing USN **3SU21CC055** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDANA M V** bearing USN **3SU21CC056** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDHANA P** bearing USN **3SU21CC057** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAVANEETH V** bearing USN **3SU21CC058** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NEHA** bearing USN **3SU21CC059** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIVEDH KRISHNA** bearing USN **3SU21CC060** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PANVITH A** bearing USN **3SU21CC061** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PARTHIV RAJAGOPAL** bearing USN **3SU21CC062** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRANAV M** bearing USN **3SU21CC063** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RACHANA T** bearing USN **3SU21CC064** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAHUL K** bearing USN **3SU21CC065** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RANJANA VINOD KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21CC066** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RENJITHA R KRISHNAN** bearing USN **3SU21CC067** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RETHUBHEDH E** bearing USN **3SU21CC068** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIDVED K V** bearing USN **3SU21CC069** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROHIT K** bearing USN **3SU21CC070** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **S VIJITH PRASAD** bearing USN **3SU21CC071** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJAY P** bearing USN **3SU21CC072** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJAY SANTHOSH S** bearing USN **3SU21CC073** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJU ANAND M** bearing USN **3SU21CC074** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAZIYA A S** bearing USN **3SU21CC075** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SIBIN BABY** bearing USN **3SU21CC076** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SNEHA S KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21CC077** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SNEHAL KUMAR K S** bearing USN **3SU21CC078** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SONA BENCHAMIN** bearing USN **3SU21CC079** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEHARI K** bearing USN **3SU21CC080** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEKANTH S** bearing USN **3SU21CC081** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEKUMARAN NAMBOOTHIRI K S** bearing USN **3SU21CC082** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREERAG K** bearing USN **3SU21CC083** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREYAS K** bearing USN **3SU21CC084** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **TITO RETTY** bearing USN **3SU21CC085** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THRISHA B S** bearing USN **3SU21CC086** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHNAV C K** bearing USN **3SU21CC087** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHNAVI** bearing USN **3SU21CC088** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIGNESH RAJESH SUNDRANI** bearing USN **3SU21CC089** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIJESH VIDYADHARAN** bearing USN **3SU21CC090** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHNU LAL K** bearing USN **3SU21CC091** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHNU NARAYANAN K** bearing USN **3SU21CC092** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISMAYA SUNEESH. K** bearing USN **3SU21CC095** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWIN K P** bearing USN **3SU21CC096** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHABEEB K** bearing USN **3SU21CC097** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL KHADER SHAMALNAZ** bearing USN **3SU21SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHINAV K** bearing USN **3SU21SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AFEEF AHMED** bearing USN **3SU21SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHMAD SHAFEEK** bearing USN **3SU21SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AISHWARYA GANESH HEGDE** bearing USN **3SU21SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH B** bearing USN **3SU21SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH S** bearing USN **3SU21SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHNAS V A** bearing USN **3SU21SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALAN K WILSON** bearing USN **3SU21SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALBIN THOMAS** bearing USN **3SU21SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEN ALEYAS** bearing USN **3SU21SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEN JOSE** bearing USN **3SU21SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALI HASSAN JUNAID J** bearing USN **3SU21SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMAN S SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU21SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMEENA SABEEBA** bearing USN **3SU21SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUSHREE S** bearing USN **3SU21SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANVITH SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU21SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AREEF M K** bearing USN **3SU21SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARJUN SASEENDRAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHISH SINGH PANWAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHWIN RAMESH** bearing USN **3SU21SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHWINI VENUGOPAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AZAD KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **B MDARSHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHAVISH B** bearing USN **3SU21SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHOOMIKA** bearing USN **3SU21SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CP MOHAMMED AMEEN** bearing USN **3SU21SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHIRAJ KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHIRAG R J** bearing USN **3SU21SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DANUSH KUMAR M** bearing USN **3SU21SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DARSHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DIMPAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DIVYAJAYA J** bearing USN **3SU21SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ENOSH KENNETH PRABHAKAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **EWAPAKA PHAWA** bearing USN **3SU21SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FARHAN RASHEED KAMAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FATHIMA PARAMBAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FATHIMATH MEHAK** bearing USN **3SU21SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FEBIN SUNNY** bearing USN **3SU21SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MORE GAURESH AJIT** bearing USN **3SU21SA040** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARIKIRANA A P** bearing USN **3SU21SA041** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM BADSHAW** bearing USN **3SU21SA042** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM MOHAMMED SAHAF** bearing USN **3SU21SA043** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JANEES P A** bearing USN **3SU21SA044** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JIBIN KURIAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA045** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JISHNU** bearing USN **3SU21SA046** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JOYEL KIRAN PINTO** bearing USN **3SU21SA047** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K ASHISH KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA048** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K H MAHAMMAD MASOOD** bearing USN **3SU21SA049** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K VIKAS RAO** bearing USN **3SU21SA050** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K Y JOEL** bearing USN **3SU21SA051** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK** bearing USN **3SU21SA052** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAUSHIK N** bearing USN **3SU21SA053** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAVYA M S** bearing USN **3SU21SA054** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA C** bearing USN **3SU21SA055** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KUSHI R** bearing USN **3SU21SA056** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAVANEESH S P** bearing USN **3SU21SA057** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHESH** bearing USN **3SU21SA058** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANIKANTAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA059** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANJUNATH SHET** bearing USN **3SU21SA060** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MASHOOD B M** bearing USN **3SU21SA061** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED HASAN AZMAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA062** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED VASEEM** bearing USN **3SU21SA063** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FAZIL** bearing USN **3SU21SA064** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD HASHIL** bearing USN **3SU21SA065** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD NIFAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA066** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED RIFAZ** bearing USN **3SU21SA067** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ADHIL C H** bearing USN **3SU21SA068** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AFREED** bearing USN **3SU21SA069** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU21SA070** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANEES** bearing USN **3SU21SA071** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASHIQ** bearing USN **3SU21SA072** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FAHEEM LATHEEF K P** bearing USN **3SU21SA073** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARDEEN** bearing USN **3SU21SA074** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARHAZ KHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA075** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FAZIL** bearing USN **3SU21SA076** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED HASSAN JAWAD** bearing USN **3SU21SA077** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED JAMSHEER C.P** bearing USN **3SU21SA078** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED KALANDER B R** bearing USN **3SU21SA079** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MUSTHAFA** bearing USN **3SU21SA080** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NABHAN K** bearing USN **3SU21SA081** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NIHAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA082** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SAHEL S** bearing USN **3SU21SA083** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAZ** bearing USN **3SU21SA084** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ZAHEER HUSSAIN** bearing USN **3SU21SA085** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOIDEEN SAHAD** bearing USN **3SU21SA086** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUEENUDDEN NAWAZ** bearing USN **3SU21SA087** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHAMMAD AFZAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA088** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED MISHAL U V** bearing USN **3SU21SA089** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED RIFAD P C** bearing USN **3SU21SA090** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED RISHAL N.K** bearing USN **3SU21SA091** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAMAL RAFEEK** bearing USN **3SU21SA092** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAMIL M T** bearing USN **3SU21SA093** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHYADDEEN NASIM** bearing USN **3SU21SA094** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NABEEL K P** bearing USN **3SU21SA095** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAFEESATHUL HAADIYAH** bearing USN **3SU21SA096** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAIK PRATVI MOHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA097** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NARESH ULLAS NAIK** bearing USN **3SU21SA098** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NEYEEMA C M** bearing USN **3SU21SA099** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIHAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA100** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIKHITHA M G** bearing USN **3SU21SA101** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **P RAHUL RAJ** bearing USN **3SU21SA102** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PAVAN RAJ** bearing USN **3SU21SA103** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **POORNESH KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA104** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAJWAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA105** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAJWAL K S** bearing USN **3SU21SA106** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAMEETH** bearing USN **3SU21SA107** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PUJARY ABHINAV ANIL** bearing USN **3SU21SA108** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PUNYA J V** bearing USN **3SU21SA109** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RACHANA JN** bearing USN **3SU21SA111** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAKESH K N** bearing USN **3SU21SA112** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAKSHA** bearing USN **3SU21SA113** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAMPRASAD N A** bearing USN **3SU21SA114** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAMNATH SHANBHAG B** bearing USN **3SU21SA115** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIFAZ AHAMED** bearing USN **3SU21SA116** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROHAN RAVI GOUDA** bearing USN **3SU21SA117** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RONIT PHILIP** bearing USN **3SU21SA118** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANIHA** bearing USN **3SU21SA119** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SATHVIKA U S** bearing USN **3SU21SA120** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAVITA VISHNOI** bearing USN **3SU21SA121** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SEBASTIAN JOSEPH** bearing USN **3SU21SA122** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHASHANK B KHARVI** bearing USN **3SU21SA123** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRAVAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA124** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRAVYA K** bearing USN **3SU21SA125** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREEJA** bearing USN **3SU21SA126** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREERAKSHA B V** bearing USN **3SU21SA127** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREYAS E U** bearing USN **3SU21SA128** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRIDHAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA129** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SIMPANA S U** bearing USN **3SU21SA130** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SOHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA131** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SOORAJ BIST** bearing USN **3SU21SA132** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEJESH K** bearing USN **3SU21SA133** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREELAYA.P.V** bearing USN **3SU21SA134** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SRI RAKSHA** bearing USN **3SU21SA135** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUKANYA PADMANABHA HEGDE** bearing USN **3SU21SA136** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUSHANTH M S** bearing USN **3SU21SA137** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SWEEKAR D S BANGERA** bearing USN **3SU21SA138** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **TANMAYA S AIL** bearing USN **3SU21SA139** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THALHATH P.P** bearing USN **3SU21SA140** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THALATUL ANSHARI** bearing USN **3SU21SA141** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THOUFIQ M H** bearing USN **3SU21SA142** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **TUSHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA143** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHNAV VIJAY P K** bearing USN **3SU21SA144** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VARSHA RAMESH NAIK** bearing USN **3SU21SA145** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VARSHA R A** bearing USN **3SU21SA146** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VINISHA SHAINY FERRAO** bearing USN **3SU21SA147** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIBHASHREE B S** bearing USN **3SU21SA148** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMAD ASHRAF** bearing USN **3SU21SA149** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KHADEEJATH SHAMA AHMED SHAFEEQ** bearing USN **3SU21SA150** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAIBHAV P P** bearing USN **3SU21SA151** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL ANSHAD M A** bearing USN **3SU21AI001** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL NUSRATH NUFAIS** bearing USN **3SU21AI002** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHINAV P P** bearing USN **3SU21AI003** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHINAV C** bearing USN **3SU21AI004** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK P** bearing USN **3SU21AI005** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED ANAS NIHAL** bearing USN **3SU21AI006** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH CHANDRA** bearing USN **3SU21AI007** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHAY S** bearing USN **3SU21AI008** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALAN TITUS** bearing USN **3SU21AI009** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANANDHU KS** bearing USN **3SU21AI010** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWIN KRISHNA T** bearing USN **3SU21AI011** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ATHITHYA M N** bearing USN **3SU21AI012** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AVINASH ASWIN** bearing USN **3SU21AI013** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FEBIN JAISON T** bearing USN **3SU21AI014** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FEDIN BINOY** bearing USN **3SU21AI015** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOKUL V GOPAL** bearing USN **3SU21AI016** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARIKRISHNAN P** bearing USN **3SU21AI017** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JUVAID FARHAN THEKUPURAM** bearing USN **3SU21AI018** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA KRISHNAN** bearing USN **3SU21AI019** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LEKSHMI SHALY** bearing USN **3SU21AI020** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SHAHBAS SULTHAN C B** bearing USN **3SU21AI021** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED YASEEN M S** bearing USN **3SU21AI022** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FAIS** bearing USN **3SU21AI023** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASHMAR** bearing USN **3SU21AI024** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED BATHISH B** bearing USN **3SU21AI025** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED BILAL K** bearing USN **3SU21AI026** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED HASAN SHIFNAN** bearing USN **3SU21AI027** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMAD INSHAF B** bearing USN **3SU21AI028** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED JAMSHEER P** bearing USN **3SU21AI029** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MAHSHEYIN M N**, bearing USN **3SU21AI030** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NIHAL ISMAIL P** bearing USN **3SU21AI031** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUBASHIR C** bearing USN **3SU21AI032** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED BISHARATH B K**, bearing USN **3SU21AI033** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED FAYIS P** bearing USN **3SU21AI034** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED MUSTHAFA** bearing USN **3SU21AI035** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED RAZI A** bearing USN **3SU21AI036** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SAHIL A NAVAS** bearing USN **3SU21AI037** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SALMAN ABOOBACKER** bearing USN **3SU21AI038** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAFI M** bearing USN **3SU21AI039** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAHEEN P H** bearing USN **3SU21AI040** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ZAYAN SADIQUE** bearing USN **3SU21AI041** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ZAYED BIN LATHEEF K P** bearing USN **3SU21AI042** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUZAMMIL K**, bearing USN **3SU21AI043** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAWAF** bearing USN **3SU21AI044** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SACHIN V N** bearing USN **3SU21AI045** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANIKA P** bearing USN **3SU21AI046** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHANO SASI** bearing USN **3SU21AI047** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHEIK THANSEER** bearing USN **3SU21AI048** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SINAN V K** bearing USN **3SU21AI049** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SOHAL PUTHAN PURAYIL**, bearing USN **3SU21AI050** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISWANTH K P** bearing USN **3SU21AI051** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL SAMAD M** bearing USN **3SU21AI052** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMAL A R** bearing USN **3SU21AI053** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **A GOUTHAM** bearing USN **3SU21CC001** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL KHADER M H** bearing USN **3SU21CC002** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAZIQ** bearing USN **3SU21CC003** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHAY PRAKASH** bearing USN **3SU21CC004** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHIJITH K** bearing USN **3SU21CC005** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHIJITH M** bearing USN **3SU21CC006** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHINAV NARAYANAN** bearing USN **3SU21CC007** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHIRAM K M** bearing USN **3SU21CC008** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK S** bearing USN **3SU21CC009** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABIN R C** bearing USN **3SU21CC010** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADHISH M** bearing USN **3SU21CC011** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AISWARYA N K** bearing USN **3SU21CC012** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH C P** bearing USN **3SU21CC013** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH S S** bearing USN **3SU21CC014** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH V** bearing USN **3SU21CC015** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKBARSHA NAVAS** bearing USN **3SU21CC016** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHIL C** bearing USN **3SU21CC017** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHILRAJ V P** bearing USN **3SU21CC018** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHIL SONICHAN** bearing USN **3SU21CC019** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHAY MADHU** bearing USN **3SU21CC020** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALFEEN RASSAK** bearing USN **3SU21CC021** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMAL T** bearing USN **3SU21CC022** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMISH V** bearing USN **3SU21CC023** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANJITHA K** bearing USN **3SU21CC024** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUAY** bearing USN **3SU21CC025** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUSREE ADIYODI VEETIL** bearing USN **3SU21CC026** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARJUN E S** bearing USN **3SU21CC027** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARJUN MANOJ** bearing USN **3SU21CC028** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWANTH B B** bearing USN **3SU21CC029** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWIN A T** bearing USN **3SU21CC030** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AYISHA SIDHEEKHA S** bearing USN **3SU21CC031** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BRINO PAUL** bearing USN **3SU21CC032** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DARSHAN T** bearing USN **3SU21CC033** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEPIKA R NAIK** bearing USN **3SU21CC034** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANUSH G** bearing USN **3SU21CC035** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOPIKA SUNIL** bearing USN **3SU21CC036** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOUDHAM SANKAR E K** bearing USN **3SU21CC037** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JAVAD HUSSAIN B** bearing USN **3SU21CC038** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JISHNU NARAYANAN K** bearing USN **3SU21CC039** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK P K** bearing USN **3SU21CC040** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KIRAN P K** bearing USN **3SU21CC041** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KIRAN RAJEEV K V** bearing USN **3SU21CC042** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRISHNAN S NAIR** bearing USN **3SU21CC043** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FAWAZ T B** bearing USN **3SU21CC044** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NASHATH** bearing USN **3SU21CC045** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHAI F B** bearing USN **3SU21CC046** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUFEEED M** bearing USN **3SU21CC047** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMAD MIRSHAD** bearing USN **3SU21CC048** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMAD HISHAM** bearing USN **3SU21CC049** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ABU THAHIR T K** bearing USN **3SU21CC050** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AYMAN E M** bearing USN **3SU21CC051** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED JASEEM T H** bearing USN **3SU21CC052** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED RIYAS B** bearing USN **3SU21CC053** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SUHAIL P C** bearing USN **3SU21CC054** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDAKISHOR S** bearing USN **3SU21CC055** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDANA M V** bearing USN **3SU21CC056** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDHANA P** bearing USN **3SU21CC057** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAVANEETH V** bearing USN **3SU21CC058** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NEHA** bearing USN **3SU21CC059** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIVEDH KRISHNA** bearing USN **3SU21CC060** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PANVITH A** bearing USN **3SU21CC061** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PARTHIV RAJAGOPAL** bearing USN **3SU21CC062** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRANAV M** bearing USN **3SU21CC063** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RACHANA T** bearing USN **3SU21CC064** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAHUL K** bearing USN **3SU21CC065** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RANJANA VINOD KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21CC066** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RENJITHA R KRISHNAN** bearing USN **3SU21CC067** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RETHUBHEDH E** bearing USN **3SU21CC068** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIDVED K V** bearing USN **3SU21CC069** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROHIT K** bearing USN **3SU21CC070** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **S VIJITH PRASAD** bearing USN **3SU21CC071** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJAY P** bearing USN **3SU21CC072** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJAY SANTHOSH S** bearing USN **3SU21CC073** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJU ANAND M** bearing USN **3SU21CC074** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAZIYA A S** bearing USN **3SU21CC075** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SIBIN BABY** bearing USN **3SU21CC076** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SNEHA S KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21CC077** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SNEHAL KUMAR K S** bearing USN **3SU21CC078** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SONA BENCHAMIN** bearing USN **3SU21CC079** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEHARI K** bearing USN **3SU21CC080** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEKANTH S** bearing USN **3SU21CC081** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEKUMARAN NAMBOOTHIRI K S** bearing USN **3SU21CC082** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREERAG K** bearing USN **3SU21CC083** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREYAS K** bearing USN **3SU21CC084** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **TITO RETTY** bearing USN **3SU21CC085** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THRISHA B S** bearing USN **3SU21CC086** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHNAV C K** bearing USN **3SU21CC087** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHNAVI** bearing USN **3SU21CC088** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIGNESH RAJESH SUNDRANI** bearing USN **3SU21CC089** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIJESH VIDYADHARAN** bearing USN **3SU21CC090** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHNU LAL K** bearing USN **3SU21CC091** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHNU NARAYANAN K** bearing USN **3SU21CC092** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHNU P** bearing USN **3SU21CC093** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHNU P** bearing USN **3SU21CC094** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISMAYA SUNEESH. K** bearing USN **3SU21CC095** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWIN K P** bearing USN **3SU21CC096** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHABEEB K** bearing USN **3SU21CC097** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL KHADER SHAMALNAZ** bearing USN **3SU21SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHINAV K** bearing USN **3SU21SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AFEEF AHMED** bearing USN **3SU21SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHMAD SHAFEEK** bearing USN **3SU21SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AISHWARYA GANESH HEGDE** bearing USN **3SU21SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH B** bearing USN **3SU21SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH S** bearing USN **3SU21SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHNAS V A** bearing USN **3SU21SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALAN K WILSON** bearing USN **3SU21SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALBIN THOMAS** bearing USN **3SU21SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEN ALEYNAS** bearing USN **3SU21SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEN JOSE** bearing USN **3SU21SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALI HASSAN JUNAID J** bearing USN **3SU21SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMAN S SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU21SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMEENA SABEEBA** bearing USN **3SU21SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUSHREE S** bearing USN **3SU21SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANVITH SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU21SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AREEF M K** bearing USN **3SU21SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARJUN SASEENDRAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHISH SINGH PANWAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHWIN RAMESH** bearing USN **3SU21SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHWINI VENUGOPAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AZAD KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **B MDARSHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHAVISH B** bearing USN **3SU21SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHOOMIKA** bearing USN **3SU21SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CP MOHAMMED AMEEN** bearing USN **3SU21SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHIRAJ KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHIRAG R J** bearing USN **3SU21SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DANUSH KUMAR M** bearing USN **3SU21SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DARSHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DIMPAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DIVYAJAYA J** bearing USN **3SU21SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ENOSH KENNETH PRABHAKAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **EWAPAKA PHAWA** bearing USN **3SU21SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FARHAN RASHEED KAMAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FATHIMA PARAMBAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FATHIMATH MEHAK** bearing USN **3SU21SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FEBIN SUNNY** bearing USN **3SU21SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MORE GAURESH AJIT** bearing USN **3SU21SA040** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARIKIRANA A P** bearing USN **3SU21SA041** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM BADSHAW** bearing USN **3SU21SA042** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM MOHAMMED SAHAF** bearing USN **3SU21SA043** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JANEES P A** bearing USN **3SU21SA044** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JIBIN KURIAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA045** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JISHNU** bearing USN **3SU21SA046** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JOYEL KIRAN PINTO** bearing USN **3SU21SA047** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K ASHISH KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA048** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K H MAHAMMAD MASOOD** bearing USN **3SU21SA049** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K VIKAS RAO** bearing USN **3SU21SA050** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K Y JOEL** bearing USN **3SU21SA051** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK** bearing USN **3SU21SA052** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAUSHIK N** bearing USN **3SU21SA053** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAVYA M S** bearing USN **3SU21SA054** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA C** bearing USN **3SU21SA055** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KUSHI R** bearing USN **3SU21SA056** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAVANEESH S P** bearing USN **3SU21SA057** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHESH** bearing USN **3SU21SA058** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANIKANTAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA059** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANJUNATH SHET** bearing USN **3SU21SA060** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MASHOOD B M** bearing USN **3SU21SA061** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED HASAN AZMAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA062** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED VASEEM** bearing USN **3SU21SA063** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FAZIL** bearing USN **3SU21SA064** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD HASHIL** bearing USN **3SU21SA065** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD NIFAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA066** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED RIFAZ** bearing USN **3SU21SA067** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ADHIL C H** bearing USN **3SU21SA068** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AFREED** bearing USN **3SU21SA069** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU21SA070** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANEES** bearing USN **3SU21SA071** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASHIQ** bearing USN **3SU21SA072** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FAHEEM LATHEEF K P** bearing USN **3SU21SA073** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARDEEN** bearing USN **3SU21SA074** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARHAZ KHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA075** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FAZIL** bearing USN **3SU21SA076** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED HASSAN JAWAD** bearing USN **3SU21SA077** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED JAMSHEER C.P** bearing USN **3SU21SA078** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED KALANDER B R** bearing USN **3SU21SA079** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MUSTHAFA** bearing USN **3SU21SA080** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NABHAN K** bearing USN **3SU21SA081** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NIHAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA082** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SAHEL S** bearing USN **3SU21SA083** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAZ** bearing USN **3SU21SA084** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ZAHEER HUSSAIN** bearing USN **3SU21SA085** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOIDEEN SAHAD** bearing USN **3SU21SA086** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUEENUDDEN NAWAZ** bearing USN **3SU21SA087** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHAMMAD AFZAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA088** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED MISHAL U V** bearing USN **3SU21SA089** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED RIFAD P C** bearing USN **3SU21SA090** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED RISHAL N.K** bearing USN **3SU21SA091** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAMAL RAFEEK** bearing USN **3SU21SA092** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAMIL M T** bearing USN **3SU21SA093** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHYADDEEN NASIM** bearing USN **3SU21SA094** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NABEEL K P** bearing USN **3SU21SA095** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAFEESATHUL HAADIYAH** bearing USN **3SU21SA096** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAIK PRATVI MOHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA097** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NARESH ULLAS NAIK** bearing USN **3SU21SA098** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NEYEEMA C M** bearing USN **3SU21SA099** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIHAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA100** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIKHITHA M G** bearing USN **3SU21SA101** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **P RAHUL RAJ** bearing USN **3SU21SA102** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PAVAN RAJ** bearing USN **3SU21SA103** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **POORNESH KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA104** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAJWAL** bearing USN **3SU21SA105** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAJWAL K S** bearing USN **3SU21SA106** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAMEETH** bearing USN **3SU21SA107** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PUJARY ABHINAV ANIL** bearing USN **3SU21SA108** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PUNYA J V** bearing USN **3SU21SA109** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RACHANA J N** bearing USN **3SU21SA111** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAKESH K N** bearing USN **3SU21SA112** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAKSHA** bearing USN **3SU21SA113** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAMPRASAD N A** bearing USN **3SU21SA114** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAMNATH SHANBHAG B** bearing USN **3SU21SA115** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIFAZ AHAMED** bearing USN **3SU21SA116** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROHAN RAVI GOUDA** bearing USN **3SU21SA117** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RONIT PHILIP** bearing USN **3SU21SA118** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANIHA** bearing USN **3SU21SA119** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SATHVIKA US** bearing USN **3SU21SA120** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAVITA VISHNOI** bearing USN **3SU21SA121** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SEBASTIAN JOSEPH** bearing USN **3SU21SA122** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHASHANK B KHARVI** bearing USN **3SU21SA123** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRAVAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA124** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRAVYA K** bearing USN **3SU21SA125** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREEJA** bearing USN **3SU21SA126** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREERAKSHA B V** bearing USN **3SU21SA127** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREYAS E U** bearing USN **3SU21SA128** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRIDHAR** bearing USN **3SU21SA129** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SIMPANA S U** bearing USN **3SU21SA130** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SOHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA131** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SOORAJ BIST** bearing USN **3SU21SA132** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEJESH K** bearing USN **3SU21SA133** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREELAYA.P.V** bearing USN **3SU21SA134** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SRI RAKSHA** bearing USN **3SU21SA135** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUKANYA PADMANABHA HEGDE** bearing USN **3SU21SA136** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUSHANTH M S** bearing USN **3SU21SA137** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SWEEKAR D S BANGERA** bearing USN **3SU21SA138** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **TANMAYA S AIL** bearing USN **3SU21SA139** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THALHATH P.P** bearing USN **3SU21SA140** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THALATUL ANSHARI** bearing USN **3SU21SA141** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THOUFIQ MH** bearing USN **3SU21SA142** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **TUSHAN** bearing USN **3SU21SA143** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHNAV VIJAY P K** bearing USN **3SU21SA144** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VARSHA RAMESH NAIK** bearing USN **3SU21SA145** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VARSHA R A** bearing USN **3SU21SA146** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VINISHA SHAINY FERRAO** bearing USN **3SU21SA147** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIBHASHREE B S** bearing USN **3SU21SA148** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMAD ASHRAF** bearing USN **3SU21SA149** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KHADEEJATH SHAMA AHMED SHAFEEQ** bearing USN **3SU21SA150** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAIBHAV P P** bearing USN **3SU21SA151** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL ANSHAD M A** bearing USN **3SU21AI001** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL NUSRATH NUFAIS** bearing USN **3SU21AI002** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHINAV P P** bearing USN **3SU21AI003** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHINAV C** bearing USN **3SU21AI004** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK P** bearing USN **3SU21AI005** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED ANAS NIHAL** bearing USN **3SU21AI006** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH CHANDRA** bearing USN **3SU21AI007** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHAY S** bearing USN **3SU21AI008** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALAN TITUS** bearing USN **3SU21AI009** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANANDHU KS** bearing USN **3SU21AI010** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWIN KRISHNA T** bearing USN **3SU21AI011** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ATHITHYA M N** bearing USN **3SU21AI012** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AVINASH ASWIN** bearing USN **3SU21AI013** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FEBIN JAISON T** bearing USN **3SU21AI014** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FEDIN BINOY** bearing USN **3SU21AI015** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOKUL V GOPAL** bearing USN **3SU21AI016** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARIKRISHNAN P** bearing USN **3SU21AI017** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JUVAID FARHAN THEKUPURAM** bearing USN **3SU21AI018** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA KRISHNAN** bearing USN **3SU21AI019** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LEKSHMI SHALY** bearing USN **3SU21AI020** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SHAHBAS SULTHAN C B** bearing USN **3SU21AI021** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED YASEEN M S** bearing USN **3SU21AI022** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FAIS** bearing USN **3SU21AI023** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASHMAR** bearing USN **3SU21AI024** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED BATHISH B** bearing USN **3SU21AI025** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED BILAL K** bearing USN **3SU21AI026** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED HASAN SHIFNAN** bearing USN **3SU21AI027** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMAD INSHAF B** bearing USN **3SU21AI028** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED JAMSHEER P** bearing USN **3SU21AI029** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MAHSHEYIN M N**, bearing USN **3SU21AI030** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NIHAL ISMAIL P** bearing USN **3SU21AI031** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUBASHIR C** bearing USN **3SU21AI032** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED BISHARATH B K**, bearing USN **3SU21AI033** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED FAYIS P** bearing USN **3SU21AI034** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED MUSTHAFA** bearing USN **3SU21AI035** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED RAZI A** bearing USN **3SU21AI036** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SAHIL A NAVAS** bearing USN **3SU21AI037** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SALMAN ABOOBACKER** bearing USN **3SU21AI038** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAFI M** bearing USN **3SU21AI039** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAHEEN P H** bearing USN **3SU21AI040** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ZAYAN SADIQUE** bearing USN **3SU21AI041** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ZAYED BIN LATHEEF K P** bearing USN **3SU21AI042** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUZAMMIL K**, bearing USN **3SU21AI043** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAWAF** bearing USN **3SU21AI044** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SACHIN V N** bearing USN **3SU21AI045** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANIKA P** bearing USN **3SU21AI046** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHANO SASI** bearing USN **3SU21AI047** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHEIK THANSEER** bearing USN **3SU21AI048** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SINAN V K** bearing USN **3SU21AI049** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SOHAL PUTHAN PURAYIL**, bearing USN **3SU21AI050** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISWANTH K P** bearing USN **3SU21AI051** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL SAMAD M** bearing USN **3SU21AI052** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMAL A R** bearing USN **3SU21AI053** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **A GOUTHAM** bearing USN **3SU21CC001** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL KHADER M H** bearing USN **3SU21CC002** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAZIQ** bearing USN **3SU21CC003** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHAY PRAKASH** bearing USN **3SU21CC004** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHIJITH K** bearing USN **3SU21CC005** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHIJITH M** bearing USN **3SU21CC006** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHINAV NARAYANAN** bearing USN **3SU21CC007** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHIRAM K M** bearing USN **3SU21CC008** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK S** bearing USN **3SU21CC009** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABIN R C** bearing USN **3SU21CC010** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADHISH M** bearing USN **3SU21CC011** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AISWARYA N K** bearing USN **3SU21CC012** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH C P** bearing USN **3SU21CC013** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH S S** bearing USN **3SU21CC014** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH V** bearing USN **3SU21CC015** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKBARSHA NAVAS** bearing USN **3SU21CC016** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHIL C** bearing USN **3SU21CC017** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHILRAJ V P** bearing USN **3SU21CC018** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHIL SONICHAN** bearing USN **3SU21CC019** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHAY MADHU** bearing USN **3SU21CC020** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALFEEN RASSAK** bearing USN **3SU21CC021** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMAL T** bearing USN **3SU21CC022** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMISH V** bearing USN **3SU21CC023** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANJITHA K** bearing USN **3SU21CC024** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUAY** bearing USN **3SU21CC025** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUSREE ADIYODI VEETIL** bearing USN **3SU21CC026** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARJUN E S** bearing USN **3SU21CC027** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARJUN MANOJ** bearing USN **3SU21CC028** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWANTH B B** bearing USN **3SU21CC029** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWIN A T** bearing USN **3SU21CC030** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AYISHA SIDHEEKHA S** bearing USN **3SU21CC031** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BRINO PAUL** bearing USN **3SU21CC032** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DARSHAN T** bearing USN **3SU21CC033** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEPIKA R NAIK** bearing USN **3SU21CC034** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANUSH G** bearing USN **3SU21CC035** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOPIKA SUNIL** bearing USN **3SU21CC036** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOUDHAM SANKAR E K** bearing USN **3SU21CC037** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JAVAD HUSSAIN B** bearing USN **3SU21CC038** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JISHNU NARAYANAN K** bearing USN **3SU21CC039** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK P K** bearing USN **3SU21CC040** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KIRAN P K** bearing USN **3SU21CC041** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KIRAN RAJEEV K V** bearing USN **3SU21CC042** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRISHNAN S NAIR** bearing USN **3SU21CC043** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FAWAZ T B** bearing USN **3SU21CC044** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NASHATH** bearing USN **3SU21CC045** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHAI F B** bearing USN **3SU21CC046** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUFEEED M** bearing USN **3SU21CC047** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMAD MIRSHAD** bearing USN **3SU21CC048** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMAD HISHAM** bearing USN **3SU21CC049** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ABU THAHIR T K** bearing USN **3SU21CC050** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AYMAN E M** bearing USN **3SU21CC051** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED JASEEM T H** bearing USN **3SU21CC052** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED RIYAS B** bearing USN **3SU21CC053** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SUHAIL P C** bearing USN **3SU21CC054** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDAKISHOR S** bearing USN **3SU21CC055** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDANA M V** bearing USN **3SU21CC056** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDHANA P** bearing USN **3SU21CC057** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAVANEETH V** bearing USN **3SU21CC058** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NEHA** bearing USN **3SU21CC059** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIVEDH KRISHNA** bearing USN **3SU21CC060** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PANVITH A** bearing USN **3SU21CC061** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PARTHIV RAJAGOPAL** bearing USN **3SU21CC062** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRANAV M** bearing USN **3SU21CC063** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RACHANA T** bearing USN **3SU21CC064** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAHUL K** bearing USN **3SU21CC065** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RANJANA VINOD KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21CC066** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RENJITHA R KRISHNAN** bearing USN **3SU21CC067** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RETHUBHEDH E** bearing USN **3SU21CC068** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIDVED K V** bearing USN **3SU21CC069** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROHIT K** bearing USN **3SU21CC070** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **S VIJITH PRASAD** bearing USN **3SU21CC071** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJAY P** bearing USN **3SU21CC072** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJAY SANTHOSH S** bearing USN **3SU21CC073** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJU ANAND M** bearing USN **3SU21CC074** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAZIYA A S** bearing USN **3SU21CC075** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SIBIN BABY** bearing USN **3SU21CC076** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SNEHA S KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU21CC077** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SNEHAL KUMAR K S** bearing USN **3SU21CC078** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SONA BENCHAMIN** bearing USN **3SU21CC079** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEHARI K** bearing USN **3SU21CC080** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEKANTH S** bearing USN **3SU21CC081** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEKUMARAN NAMBOOTHIRI K S** bearing USN **3SU21CC082** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREERAG K** bearing USN **3SU21CC083** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREYAS K** bearing USN **3SU21CC084** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **TITO RETTY** bearing USN **3SU21CC085** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THRISHA B S** bearing USN **3SU21CC086** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHNAV C K** bearing USN **3SU21CC087** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHNAVI** bearing USN **3SU21CC088** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIGNESH RAJESH SUNDRANI** bearing USN **3SU21CC089** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIJESH VIDYADHARAN** bearing USN **3SU21CC090** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHNU LAL K** bearing USN **3SU21CC091** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHNU NARAYANAN K** bearing USN **3SU21CC092** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHNU P** bearing USN **3SU21CC093** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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Mangaluru - 575 001

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Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHNU P** bearing USN **3SU21CC094** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISMAYA SUNEESH. K** bearing USN **3SU21CC095** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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DEAN
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWIN K P** bearing USN **3SU21CC096** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the III SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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DEAN
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHABEEB K** bearing USN **3SU21CC097** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
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